

ON SOLVING NON-HOMOGENEOUS TERNARY QUINTIC DIOPHANTINE EQUATION

$$w^2 + 2z^2 - 2wx - 4zx = x^5 - 3x^2$$

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ABSTRACT:

The non-homogeneous ternary fifth degree Diophantine equation given by $w^2 + 2z^2 - 2wx - 4zx = x^5 - 3x^2$ is analyzed for its patterns of non-zero distinct integral solutions..

KEYWORDS: Ternary quintic equation ,Non- Homogeneous quintic equation , Integral solutions

INTRODUCTION:

The Diophantine equation offers an unlimited field for research due to their variety [1-4]. In particular, one may refer [5-10] for quintic equations with two ,three and five unknowns. This communication concerns with yet another interesting equation $w^2 + 2z^2 - 2wx - 4zx = x^5 - 3x^2$ representing non-homogeneous quintic with three unknowns for determining its infinitely many non-zero integral points.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS:

The given non-homogeneous ternary quintic Diophantine equation is

$$w^2 + 2z^2 - 2wx - 4zx = x^5 - 3x^2 \tag{1}$$

On completing the squares,(1) is written as

$$P^2 + 2Q^2 = x^5 \tag{2}$$

where

$$P = w - x, Q = z - x \tag{3}$$

We illustrate below the process of obtaining different sets of integer solutions to (1):

Set 1:

After some algebra, it is observed that (2) is satisfied by

$$P = m(m^2 + 2n^2)^2, Q = n(m^2 + 2n^2)^2 \tag{4}$$

and

$$x = m^2 + 2n^2 \tag{5}$$

From (4) and (3), we have

$$w = [m(m^2 + 2n^2) + 1](m^2 + 2n^2), z = [n(m^2 + 2n^2) + 1](m^2 + 2n^2) \tag{6}$$

Thus, (5) and (6) represent the integer solutions to (1).

Set 2:

Assuming (5) in (2) and employing the method of factorization, one obtains

$$P + i\sqrt{2}Q = (m + i\sqrt{2}n)^5 \tag{7}$$

On equating the real and imaginary parts, we have

$$P = f(m, n), Q = g(m, n) \tag{8}$$

where

$$f(m, n) = m^5 - 20m^3n^2 + 20mn^4, \\ g(m, n) = 5m^4n - 20m^2n^3 + 4n^5$$

Using (8) in (3), note that

$$z = m^2 + 2n^2 + g(m, n), w = m^2 + 2n^2 + f(m, n) \tag{9}$$

Thus, (5) and (9) represent the integer solutions to (1).

Set 3:

Write (2) as

$$P^2 + 2Q^2 = x^5 * 1 \tag{10}$$

Consider 1 as

$$1 = \frac{(F(r,s) + i\sqrt{2} G(r,s)) (F(r,s) - i\sqrt{2} G(r,s))}{[H(r,s)]^2} \tag{11}$$

where

$$F(r,s) = 2r^2 - s^2, G(r,s) = 2rs, H(r,s) = 2r^2 + s^2$$

Using (5) and (11) in (10) and employing the method of factorization, one has

$$P + i\sqrt{2}Q = \frac{(F(r,s) + i\sqrt{2} G(r,s)) (m + i\sqrt{2}n)^5}{H(r,s)} \tag{12}$$

Equating the real and imaginary parts in (12) and replacing m by $H(r,s)M$ and n by $H(r,s)N$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} P &= [H(r,s)]^4 [f(M,N)F(r,s) - 2g(M,N)G(r,s)] \\ Q &= [H(r,s)]^4 [f(M,N)G(r,s) + g(M,N)F(r,s)] \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Also, from (5), we have

$$x = [H(r,s)]^2 (M^2 + 2N^2) \tag{14}$$

Substituting (13) and (14) in (3), one obtains the corresponding values of z, w satisfying (1).

Set 4 :

The option

$$Q = kx^2 \tag{15}$$

in (2) leads to

$$P^2 = x^4 (x - 2k^2)$$

which is satisfied by

$$x = (s^2 + 2)k^2 \tag{16}$$

and

$$P = s (s^2 + 2)^2 k^5 \tag{17}$$

Using (16) in (15), we have

$$Q = (s^2 + 2)^2 k^5 \tag{18}$$

Substituting (17) and (18) in (3), it is seen that

$$\begin{aligned} w &= (s^2 + 2)k^2 [s(s^2 + 2)k^3 + 1] \\ z &= (s^2 + 2)k^2 [(s^2 + 2)k^3 + 1] \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Thus, (16) and (19) satisfy (1).

Set 5 :

The option

$$P = x^2 \tag{20}$$

in (2) leads to

$$2Q^2 = x^4 (x - 1)$$

which is satisfied by

$$x = (2k^2 + 1) \tag{21}$$

and

$$Q = k (2k^2 + 1)^2 \tag{22}$$

Using (21) in (20) , we have

$$P = (2k^2 + 1)^2 \tag{23}$$

Substituting (21) ,(22) and (23) in (3) , it is seen that

$$\begin{aligned} w &= (2k^2 + 1)(2k^2 + 2) \\ z &= (2k^2 + 1) [k(2k^2 + 1) + 1] \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

Thus , (21) and (24) satisfy (1).

Set 6 :

The choice

$$P = k Q \tag{25}$$

in (2) gives

$$(k^2 + 2) Q^2 = x^5$$

which is satisfied by

$$Q = (k^2 + 2)^2 \alpha^{5s} \tag{26}$$

and

$$x = (k^2 + 2) \alpha^{2s} \tag{27}$$

From (25) ,it is seen that

$$P = k(k^2 + 2)^2 \alpha^{5s} \tag{28}$$

Using (26) ,(27) and (28) in (3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} w &= k(k^2 + 2)^2 \alpha^{5s} + (k^2 + 2) \alpha^{2s} \\ z &= (k^2 + 2)^2 \alpha^{5s} + (k^2 + 2) \alpha^{2s} \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

Thus , (1) is satisfied by (27) and (29).

Set 7 :

The choice

$$Q = kP$$

(30) in (2) gives

$$(2k^2 + 1) P^2 = x^5$$

which is satisfied by

$$P = (2k^2 + 1)^2 \alpha^{5s} \quad (31)$$

and

$$x = (2k^2 + 1) \alpha^{2s} \quad (32)$$

From (30), it is seen that

$$Q = k(2k^2 + 1)^2 \alpha^{5s} \quad (33)$$

Using (31), (32) and (33) in (3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} w &= (2k^2 + 1)^2 \alpha^{5s} + (2k^2 + 1) \alpha^{2s} \\ z &= k(2k^2 + 1)^2 \alpha^{5s} + (2k^2 + 1) \alpha^{2s} \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Thus, (1) is satisfied by (32) and (34).

CONCLUSION:

In this paper, we have made an attempt to obtain all integer solutions to (1). To conclude, one may search for integer solutions to other choices of homogeneous or non-homogeneous quintic equations with multiple variables.

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